

The system of lessons and lessons of mathematics in elementary grades

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Annotatsiya: Boshlang'ich sinflarda matematika darsi, uning xususiyatlari, darsni tshkil qilish tizimi, darsga qo'yilgan talablar to'g'risidagi bilimlarni mustahkamlash.

Kalit so'zlar: Dars, dars tizimi, dars mazmuni, dars tarkibi, dars tiplari, matematika darslari xususiyatlari, matematika darsi turlari: murakkab dars, yangi materialni o'rganish darsi, mustahkamlash darsi, umumlashtiruvchi dars, nazorat qilish darslari.

Аннотация: Закрепление знаний об уроке математики в начальных классах, его особенностях, системе организации урока, требованиях к проведению урока.

Ключевые слова: Урок, система урока, содержание урока, содержание урока, виды урока, особенности урока математики, виды урока математики: комплексный урок, урок для изучения нового материала, урок-закрепление, урок-обобщающий, контрольный урок.

Abstract: Strengthening knowledge about the mathematics lesson in primary grades, its features, lesson organization system, requirements for the lesson.

Key words: Lesson, lesson system, lesson content, lesson content, lesson types, features of mathematics lessons, types of mathematics lesson: complex lesson, lesson for learning new material, reinforcement lesson, summarizing lesson, control lessons.

The lesson is a historical, complex form of organizing the teaching of

mathematics at school, proven by many years of experience and meeting the basic requirements of our time. The acquisition of mathematical knowledge by students depends not only on the choice of the correct method in teaching, but also on the form of organization of the educational process.

A lesson is an educational work organized by a fixed number of students under the guidance of a teacher, according to a specific schedule, according to the program. During the lesson, students learn the theoretical information from mathematics, counting skills, problem solving, various measurements, that is, all educational work is performed in the classroom. The uniqueness of the mathematics lesson, first of all, follows from the features of this academic subject. One of its features is that, along with arithmetic material, elements of algebra and geometry are also studied. Another peculiar side of the elementary course of mathematics is the joint consideration of theoretical problems. That is why practical skills and abilities are instilled in each lesson with the introduction of new knowledge.

Usually, several didactic goals are realized in the lesson: the passage of new material; strengthening the subject; strengthening knowledge; generalization, systematization of knowledge; creating reliable learning and skills, etc. Another feature of mathematics lessons is the abstractness of the teaching material. Therefore, it also depends on visual aids, careful selection of active teaching methods, student activity, and the skill level of class students. Another requirement for modern mathematics classes is the development of independent thinking and creative activity of students. The student develops such mental operations as analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization, conclusion. The system of mathematics lessons in elementary grades - in each lesson, students work with several concepts. Each of them can be mastered at different stages of this lesson. The understanding of each concept is carried out by repetition, recall of another

concept, and this concept serves to explain the following concepts.

In the learning process, each training material is presented in expanded form, this training material is the foundation for understanding the materials taught after it. If we consider the process of mastering another concept, then it is formed as a result of the interconnected teaching of several lessons. Thus, the formation of mathematical concepts is formed not in one lesson, but in the process of passing a series of interrelated lessons. We call such classes a shared class system. Therefore, the teacher must arrange the lessons in a logical sequence that reveals the content of the subject.

The biggest requirement in the structure of the lesson system is to take into account the educational purpose of the lesson, taking into account the methodological and general pedagogical aspects of the principles of teaching. A well-thought-out system of classes on a topic depends on the correct distribution of study time by topic. It should be aimed at developing students' independence by considering specific examples, drawing specific conclusions from them and drawing general conclusions from them. After this knowledge is formed and fixed in the lesson system, examples and tasks should be solved. After that, it is necessary to develop the skills through exercises, as well as to ensure the continuous integration and generalization of the acquired knowledge. When determining the content of the topic of the program, distributing the material of the topic for class hours, that is, obtaining knowledge, the following main stages are considered.

1. Preparation of new material for training.
2. Perception of new educational material and creation of new knowledge.
3. Consolidation of knowledge and the formation of skills through various exercises.
4. Repetition, generalization and systematization of knowledge.

5. Testing knowledge and skills.

Most of the methodological literature is based on the division of lessons according to their didactic purpose. Below are the types of math lessons:

1. A lesson in mastering new knowledge. In them, students get acquainted with new concepts, calculation methods, solutions to new types of problems, new properties of figures, numbers;

2. A lesson to consolidate knowledge, skills and abilities. They work examples and tasks related to consolidating the knowledge, skills and abilities gained in the previous lesson;

3. Repetition - lessons-generalizations. Examples of this include repetition and debriefing at the end of a particular section, or at the beginning and end of a school year;

4. Lesson control of knowledge, skills and abilities.

5. A mixed or complex lesson in which there are several didactic goals, and all of them are important.

In conclusion, we can say that one of the important requirements of our time is the activation of the knowledge and creative activity of students. Each lesson should focus on thinking and creativity.

References:

1. Dzhumaev M.E. Workshop on the methodology of teaching mathematics in elementary grades. (for O O'Y) Tashkent. "Teacher" 2004
2. Dzhumaev M.E. Methodology for organizing laboratory classes in mathematics in elementary grades. Tashkent. "Generation of the new century" 2006. 20 b / t.
3. Tadzhieva Z.G., Abdullaeva B.S., Dzhumaev M.E., Sidelnikova R.I., Sadykova A.V. Methods of teaching mathematics.-T. "Turon-Iqbal" 2011. 336s.